

Investigation of the Bulk Current Injection Technique by Comparison to Induced Currents from Radiated Electromagnetic Fields

Dawn H. Trout
 NASA, George C. Marshall Space Flight Center
 MS EL23
 MSFC, AL 35812

Abstract -- Since the late 80's Bulk Current Injection (BCI) techniques have gained wide acceptance in aerospace, commercial and military Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) testing. BCI techniques provide a low cost and technically superior result to radiated techniques at low frequencies. There has always been conflict between adherents to radiated techniques and the newer BCI techniques. This investigation focuses on the degree to which BCI techniques accurately simulate the radiated mechanism of field-to-wire coupling.

BACKGROUND AND OVERVIEW

When integrating equipment into larger platforms (spacecraft, aircraft, buildings, etc.) there is a long standing problem of how to adequately address system level environmental effects in equipment level testing. Such equipment level testing representative of the environment is necessary since it is not practical to wait until platform integration for environmental testing.

Radiated susceptibility testing is one such case where equipment level testing is necessary to ensure each piece of equipment will operate in its intended electromagnetic environment. Figure 1 shows the typical radiated susceptibility test setup. Radiated susceptibility testing in the military arena has been in the 14 kHz to 40 GHz frequency range, while commercial tests are from 80 MHz to 1 GHz. Since testing is usually performed in a limited space, the entire length of associated cables of the equipment under test (EUT) is normally not in vehicle configuration and the efficiency of the radiated electromagnetic field coupling to equipment cables is diminished. Another problem associated with this method of testing at low frequencies is that the EUT is in the near field of the antenna where actual field levels are not uniform and difficult to repeat

Figure 1: Typical Radiated Susceptibility Test Setup

To combat these problems, the latest military Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) specifications (MIL-STD-461D) have added a Bulk Current Injection (BCI) method for the low frequency radiated susceptibility testing (Figure 2) [1]. In BCI current is transformer coupled onto the EUT cabling. The amount of injected current is correlated to the induced currents from environmental radiated fields in the actual system. An overlap of the BCI and antenna radiated susceptibility exists in the current MIL-STD-461D at frequencies from 10 kHz to 400 MHz.

Figure 2: Typical BCI Test Set-up

Although several organizations are now using BCI at frequencies less than 1 GHz to augment radiated equipment susceptibility testing, questions have been raised about the validity of using BCI to simulate the currents induced by a radiated field. One study showed differences from BCI induced currents and those induced from antennas onto cables of up to 40 dB [2].

This study examines the relations between radiated induced currents and BCI injected currents, compares the data from the BCI and radiated field induced currents, and determines the range where BCI effectively simulates the radiated induced coupling. Establishing a uniform plane wave to illuminate the cables is also addressed since it is suspected that the discrepancies in previous studies are due to radiated field non-uniformities.

BULK CURRENT INJECTION

The principle behind the bulk current injection technique is to use current injection directly onto equipment cables instead of radiating the equipment with the specification field. The amount of current injected corresponds to the worse case radiated field levels to which equipment is exposed. One advantage of this technique is that the entire length of equipment cable is not necessary to determine the impacts of induced currents on the equipment. This is an improvement over using radiated techniques in a test chamber where the entire length of cable is needed for a true picture of field-to-wire coupling, but where only 2 meters of cabling is used because of difficulty in fully illuminating the entire cable length. In fact, several cases have been cited where using traditional radiated susceptibility testing methods showed no susceptibilities to high frequency fields (2-3 MHz), but similar fields caused interference with equipment and cabling in the platform configuration.

In BCI testing an injection clamp similar to current probes used for military conducted emissions testing is used. In a typical BCI test set-up, BCI clamps are used to inject the specification current onto the cables under test. Current probes are used to measure the injected current. Both current probes and BCI clamps act as transformers.

A current probe acts as a transformer with a single turn primary and a multiple turn secondary. The primary places a low series impedance in the probed power line or signal lead. The secondary has a higher impedance which allows it to drive a usable signal into a 50 Ω receiver, Figure 3. A current probe is characterized by its transfer impedance, Z_t (dBΩ) the ratio of the output voltage into a standard load (usually 50Ω for EMI testing) divided by the net current traveling through the probe window area [3].

a. Physical Implementation

b. Probe Equivalent Circuit

Figure 3: Current Probe with Equivalent Circuit

A bulk current injection clamp, Figure 4, has a similar core material as the current probe but heavier windings. It acts as a transformer with a multiple turn primary and a single turn secondary when placed around a power line or signal lead. Thus it provides a nominal 50 Ω load to the signal generator (susceptibility signal source). The secondary provides a lower signal impedance when placed in series with the cable under test (CUT). A BCI clamp is characterized by its insertion loss in (dB), which describes the inefficiency of the clamp relative to direct injection into a 50 Ω circuit [3].

a. Physical Implementation

b. BCI Equivalent Circuit

Figure 4: BCI Clamp With Equivalent Circuit

PLANE WAVE ILLUMINATION

Many antennas such as a dipole antenna require large distances from the antenna to be in the far field (to achieve a uniform plane wave). The distance from an antenna where the far field begins is generally defined as $R = \frac{2(D)^2}{\lambda}$ (1)

where
 R = far field distance from the antenna,
 D = dimension of the largest antenna aperture, and
 λ = wavelength of the transmitted or received signal.
 For $D = \lambda/2$ (typical dipole), this equation reduces to:
 $R = \frac{\lambda}{2}$ (2)

Thus, even for a transmitting frequency of 30 MHz, the required distance from the antenna to achieve a uniform plane wave is 5 meters. At 100 kHz this distance increases to 1500 meters.

Since a parallel plate can be used to generate a uniform plane wave between the plates, this approach is used. To achieve a plane wave at higher frequencies than typical parallel plates, a microstrip style transmission line is used. A microstrip consists of a low loss metal plate over a ground plane (larger than the top plate) with an insulating material or substrate in between. For this experiment air is the substrate.

The parallel plate in this experiment acts as a transmission line where electrical signals propagate, ideally without attenuation. Power (S) propagates down the transmission line perpendicular to electric and magnetic fields such that $\vec{E} \times \vec{H} = \vec{S}$. The assumed coordinate system is also shown in Figure 5. It has a longitudinal coordinate z and two coordinates in the transverse plane perpendicular to z . These rectangular coordinates are x (normal to the ground plane) and y (tangential to the ground plane). The transverse dimensions (substrate height, strip width) are much smaller than a wavelength.

Figure 5: Microstrip Transmission Line

Transverse and longitudinal fields are independent of each other, or orthogonal, and may be analyzed separately.

Impedance Matching

The guide or transmission line must be matched and the signal driven in the characteristic impedance. At low frequencies the microstrip transmission line characteristic impedance is still controlled by the ratio of the inductance and capacitance of the microstrip. The following equation gives the characteristic impedance for microstrip circuits where the width of the microstrip is larger than the height as follows [4]:

$$Z_c = \frac{120\pi}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \left[\frac{w}{h_p} + 1.393 + 0.667 \ln \left(\frac{w}{h_p} + 1.444 \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_r = relative permittivity =1 for air.

Substitution into this equation $\epsilon_r = 1$ for free space, $h_p = 6$ inches and $W = 12$ inches (which are the dimensions of the plate used in the experiment) gives $Z_c = 89.38$.

Another important consideration is the height of the plate. It must be short relative to the wavelengths of interest. If h_p is generally less than $\lambda/8$, the transmission line can conduct the uniform plane wave without the plate acting like a dipole antenna [5].

Field-to-wire-coupling

The electromagnetic fields under the parallel plate approximate a uniform plane wave. The field coupling to the wires under the plate is a worst case simulation of spacecraft or aircraft antenna fields coupling to equipment cables. The current is induced onto the wire loop by electromagnetic fields. The following shows a derivation of the field-to-wire coupling calculations used to derive BCI limits. For more detailed reference see [6].

The voltage induced on a wire is found using Faraday's law as follows:

$$\oint_c \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{l} = -\frac{d}{dt} \int_s \vec{B} \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (4)$$

\vec{E} is the electric field intensity vector, with units of volts/meter (V/m). The parameter \vec{B} is the magnetic flux density vector, with units of webers/square meter (Wb/m^2).

This equation can be shown to reduce to:

$$V_i = 2E_o h \sin\left(\frac{\beta l}{2}\right) \quad \text{where} \quad \beta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

This is the equation for induced voltage in terms of the E-field, frequency and the dimensions of the loop. This expression is used to determine the induced voltage in the wires under the parallel plate in the experiment. The derived induced voltages divided by the wire and load impedances across the measured frequency range gives the induced currents which are used to compare to measured results. The impedance calculation contains resistance, inductance and an average of inductance and capacitance at higher frequencies where the distributed capacitance reaches inductance values. The average high frequency impedance for this experiment is 316 Ω .

EXPERIMENT SET-UP

Dimensions of Plate

A parallel plate is used to obtain a uniform field to illuminate the wires under test. The plate should minimize the reflection losses in the system and allow for reasonable prediction of data. The plate used was designed to maximize a uniform field while having a reasonable size for a work area to access the wires and current probes. A 50 Ω characteristic impedance is desirable for matching a signal generator, but would minimize the height of the parallel plate [7].

An example of a parallel plate with reasonable dimensions, which is usable to at least 200 MHz, and which provides sufficient electric field strength for many tests using low power signal generators as sources is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Dimensions of Test Plate over Ground Plane

The parallel plate is 12 inches wide and 6 inches tall. The length of the plate is 39.5 inches or 1 meter. The height of the plate meets the criteria that $h_p < \lambda/8$ for frequencies ≤ 200 MHz.

Matching Network for Plate

The value of the termination impedance of the plate is determined by the characteristic impedance of the parallel plate which in turn is determined by the width to height ratio. The characteristic impedance for a parallel plate with this height to width ratio is 90 Ω . The 90 Ω load impedance is implemented with a 50 Ω load and a 40 Ω load in series so that the 50 Ω load can be replaced with a 50 Ω spectrum analyzer to check the plate voltage. This load is attached at the end of the plate taper [7].

The driving end of the upper plate is also attached to a matching network so that the parallel plate is matched with its characteristic impedance of 90 Ω and the signal generator is matched with 50 Ω standard impedance.

For a 90 Ω plate, the matching values are $R_1 = 75 \Omega$, and $R_2 = 60 \Omega$.

INPUT VOLTAGE

A field of 1 volt/meter is chosen for convenience and to be within the range of the signal generator output. The loss from the matching network is accounted for by the following:

$$V_L = V_{sg} \cdot \left(\frac{90}{90+60} \right) = \frac{3}{5} \cdot V_{sg} \quad (6)$$

$$V_L = V_{sg} - 4.4dB$$

where

V_L = Voltage at the load of the parallel plate,
 V_{sg} = Voltage required by the signal generator.

The static E-field in a parallel plate can be obtained by the following equation:

$$\vec{E} = \frac{V}{h_p} \quad (7)$$

where

V = Voltage across the plate and
 h_p = plate height.

To obtain a 1 V/m field under the parallel plate when h_p is 0.15m, a voltage of 0.15 is needed on the plate. The needed voltage in dB μ V is: 0.15 V = 103.5 dB μ V. Adding the loss of the matching network the voltage required is: 103.5 dB μ V + 4.4 dB = 107.9 dB μ V. Therefore the plate is driven with 108 dB μ V from the signal generator, through the matching network, to generate a 1 V/m field under the parallel plate.

PLATE FIELDS

The E-Field and H-Field components under the plate are measured to ensure the parallel plate is producing a uniform plane wave. Using the free space impedance of 377 Ω or 51.5 dB Ω (dB above 1 Ohm), the predicted H-field is 1V/m (120 dB μ V/m) - 51.5 dB Ω = 68.5 dB μ A/m. The H - field levels were measured from the top of plate to the ground plane in four vertical locations. The locations of the H-

Field measurements are shown in Figure 7. The H-Field measured levels are shown in Figure 8 with the line labeled 1st being closest to the top of the plate. Figure 9 shows the H-Field, E-field and the field impedance measurements plotted with calculated values. These measured values correlate with the predicted H-field for a 1 V/m field (120 dB μ V/m) and a 377 Ω (51.5 dB Ω impedance) field impedance.

Figure 7: H-Field Probe and Measurement Notches

Figure 8: Parallel Plate Measured H-field Levels

Figure 9: E-field, H-field, and Field Impedance Data

The data in Figure 8 shows that the measured H-fields are within about 2 dB of predicted values across the frequency range and throughout the height of the plate. The data in Figure 9 shows the measured E-Field and H-Field data on one plot with the field

impedance and calculated values. The measured data is similar to the calculated data; thus, the electromagnetic fields generated by the parallel plate are near uniform.

PLATE VOLTAGE

The parallel plate voltage shown in Figure 10 is measured to assess for non-uniformities with increasing frequency. The voltage in the figure is measured at the load side of the plate such that losses from both source and load matching networks are present. The plate voltage is constant up to 10 MHz. The voltage is within about 2 dB of the constant up to 200 MHz except at 94 MHz (3 dB) and 172 MHz (7 dB). The plate is unstable after 200 MHz. This is acceptable since the planned measurements are below 200 MHz.

Figure 10: Measured Voltage from Top Plate to Ground

WIRE LOAD IMPEDANCES.

Three wires are used under the plate that are terminated at each end to the ground plane. The first wire is terminated with 1 Ω at each end to simulate a near short condition. This impedance is higher, but similar to that of a shield grounded at both ends. The second wire is terminated at both ends with 50 Ω , which represents typical electronics and electrical loads. The third wire is terminated at both ends with 270 Ω , a high impedance near the characteristic impedance of the wire. The high impedance loads simulate sensitive electronic circuits. The test set-up including the wires under the parallel plate are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Test Set-up

TEST PROCEDURE

The frequency range for the field-to-wire coupling and BCI injection measurements is 100 kHz to 200 MHz.

Parallel Plate - Field-to-Wire Coupling

To measure the field-to-wire induced currents, the wires are set up under the plate as in Figure 11 and illuminated with a 1 V/m field. Next, the overall bundle current induced onto the wires from the parallel plate is measured with all three wires in the probe. The last step is to measure the current induced on the individual wires with current probes.

Bulk Current Injection

To obtain the BCI induced currents at each frequency, the current value obtained from the overall bundle measurement in the parallel plate method is injected using the BCI clamp over the 3-wire bundle. With the current probes over the individual wires, the wire currents induced from the BCI clamp at each frequency for each of the 3 wires are then measured. Two BCI clamps (BCI-1 and BCI-2) are used for test accuracy. Each BCI and current probe is placed separately on the wires to preclude loading of the field under the plate.

RESULTS

Measured Combined Data with Calculated Data

Figures 12 through 14 show measured data along with calculated data. This data shows strong correlation between the BCI and parallel plate data until 100 MHz. Looking at the differences chart in Figure 15, the data shows about +/- 2 dB correlation until 80-100 MHz where the data begins to vary widely. The maximum difference is 13 dB at 100 MHz in the 1 Ω case. However, all of the load cases vary beyond 100 MHz. These differences in the parallel plate case and the BCI case can be attributed to standing waves at high frequencies during BCI injection. At the frequencies of decrease correlation between the parallel plate and BCI data the wire length is $l = \lambda/4$ and longer. The variations greater than 2 dB from the parallel plate case occur between 80-90 MHz and continue through 200 MHz. This indicates that BCI may be an unreliable means of susceptibility testing when the injection distance of the BCI clamp to the EUT approaches $\lambda/4$ of the signal frequency. This has been further confirmed by moving the measuring probe along the line and noting variations in amplitudes at the same frequency. The distance where the BCI is injected is critical when the wire length approaches $\lambda/4$.

Figure 12: Parallel Plate, BCI and Calculated Data - 1 Ω

Figure 13: Parallel Plate, BCI and Calculated Data - 50 Ω

Figure 14: Parallel Plate, BCI and Calculated Data - 270 Ω

There is also reasonable correlation for all load cases between the parallel plate measured data and the calculated data up to 100 MHz. Above 100 MHz the field-to-wire coupling or parallel plate data shows higher coupled levels than the calculated data. This difference between calculated and measured data at high frequencies can be attributed to the distributed capacitance in the system that interacts with the wire inductance to alter the line impedance. The calculated values only model the wire resistance, inductance and an average of inductance and distributed capacitance. Actual resonances are difficult to model and are not included in the calculations.

Figure 15: Parallel Plate and BCI - Differences in (dB)

CONCLUSIONS

The relatively consistent data (+/- 2 dB) between BCI and field-to-wire coupling up to 80 MHz differs from the other author's results where differences of up to 40 dB were seen [2]. Some of the possible reasons for these differences are that other measurements are taken in metallic aircraft frames where reflections could influence the radiated injection case, but would not be present during the BCI case. Also standing waves from longer cables are a factor. In one case, the minimum line length used was 3 meters. Even at the start frequency of 20 MHz the $\lambda/4$ length would be 3.75 meters. Therefore, the entire set of data may have been influenced by standing waves. Given this rationale, it is not surprising that the radiated field and BCI methods of inducing currents on cables did not compare closely.

Recommendations

The data shows good correlation until 80 to 90 MHz where the length of the wire approaches $1/4$ wavelength. Thus, it is recommended that the injection distance between the EUT and BCI clamp be short relative to a wavelength. When cables are shielded as is often the case for spacecraft and military cables, the entire length of the cable must be kept shorter than $\lambda/4$ to obtain reliable results. This follows with the way many European standards specify BCI. For example, the International Electrotechnical Committee in *IEC 1000 Conducted Immunity Requirements (4-6)* specifies BCI up to 80 MHz and uses radiated immunity (with antennas) from 80 MHz to 1 GHz. The BCI testing end frequency for this IEC standard is similar to the frequencies at which significant variation in the field-to-wire coupling method versus the BCI coupling method occurred in this experiment.

Summary

BCI testing has been verified to be a valid test at low frequencies for injecting current levels that would be induced from known electromagnetic field levels. BCI does not model platform radiated reflections; therefore, peak or worst case field levels should be used when determining the level of currents to inject with BCI. In addition, the length of wire and injection distance to the EUT must be considered. BCI can be used as a low frequency complement to high frequency radiated immunity testing to achieve a reasonable assessment of susceptibility of equipment to radiated interference.

REFERENCES

- [1]. MIL-STD-461D, "Requirements for the Control of Electromagnetic Interference Emissions and Susceptibility," January 1993.

- [2]. J. Adams and D. Melquist, "Comparison Measurements of Currents Induced by Radiation and Injection," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. EMC-34, no.3, pp. 360-362, August 1992.
- [3]. K. Javor, "The How and Why of Bulk Current Injection Testing," *EMC Test and Design*, September/October, pp. 35-40, 1992.
- [4]. C. Balanis, *Advanced Engineering Electromagnetics*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1989.
- [5]. K. Javor, *Introduction to the Control of Electromagnetic Interference*, EMC Compliance, Huntsville, AL, 1993.
- [6]. D.H. Trout, "Relationship Between Induced Currents from Bulk Current Injection Techniques versus Radiated Electromagnetic Field Illumination," University of Alabama in Huntsville Thesis, 1995.
- [7]. E. L. Bronaugh and W.S. Lambdin, *Electromagnetic Interference Test Methodology and Procedures*, Interference Control Technologies, Inc., Gainesville, VA, 1994.